

ROOT CANAL PREPARATION AS A STAGE OF TOOTH RESTORATION

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Annotation: The result of endodontic therapy undoubtedly depends on the qualitative sufficiency of all stages of work. The success of root canal filling is directly related to its optimal preparation. An indispensable condition is the removal of root canal contents, the determination of the working length following mechanical and medical procedures. All instruments are used step by step within the apical stenosis. When using a rotating instrument, follow its instructions. Mechanical treatment is accompanied by root canal irrigation. Radiological control is carried out according to the protocol of endodontic therapy. The treatment is completed by root canal filling and subsequent restoration of the tooth.

Keywords: Endodontic therapy, root canal, working length

Introduction: Endodontic therapy has undergone several important "revolutionary" changes in the course of its long development. I will not elaborate on all of them, but I will mention the Chemodonov method. The main idea of the Chemodonov method was to pull out the filler from the tips of the roots. We pursued the goal of reducing the number of visits by performing all operations in 1 stage by performing the treatment "in 1 visit" if possible. Modern approaches include the preparation of root canals to ensure three-dimensional filling up to apical stenosis [6, 7, 10]. An important stage of endodontic therapy is to determine the working length. The working length is the distance from the anatomical landmark on the crown (the incisal edge in the front tooth, usually the tip of the tooth in the chewing tooth) to the physiological (anatomical) stenosis. By performing this stage qualitatively, it is free to perform cleaning and shaping in the lumen without

damaging the surrounding tissue [3, 5, 11].Special X-ray fluoroscopy, which determines the length of the work, is the most reliable method because it allows visualization of the quality of the measurement. [2, 9].The method is based on obtaining an X-ray image of the root of the tooth inserted with an endodontic treatment instrument and measuring the distance with a special Multifix ruler.The most acceptable instrument for determining the working length is a thin flexible K-reamer (K-File) that passes well through the root canal and reaches the apical stenosis.There are biological and mechanical requirements for the preparation and formation of root canals.From a biological point of view, the purpose of root canal treatment is to remove as much as possible pulp residues, microorganisms and their substrates along with infected dentin.From a mechanical point of view, three-dimensional lumen formation is a prerequisite for high-quality lumen closure. [4, 6].The "step back" (apical-coronal) method is a method of expanding the lumen from the apical to the oral cavity using an instrument that is larger in diameter."Step down", "crown down" is a lumen enlargement method that does not need to determine the working length first.This method is based on sequential use from the mouth to the root of the tooth, from the thick instrument to the thin instrument.It is also possible to use a mixpreparation technique, in which case the first step starts from the tooth cavity towards the stenosis or curvature of the lumen.Then determine the working length and continue the wall preparation from the tip stenosis towards the mouth.The emergence of various rotating instruments has led to significant changes in the algorithm of preparation of endodontic therapy.In this regard, it plays an important role to uphold the principles of the Rotary File.That is to say, smooth and progressive movement without applying pressure in the tip direction, clear order of use, compliance with the requirements of the manufacturer, control of the frequency of use, lumen cleaning with disinfectant solution [1], 8].In some cases, it can be difficult for dentists to determine how to use the latest instruments, devices and materials most effectively.

Materials and methods: Clinical observation was carried out under the conditions of a dental clinic equipped with the latest equipment, instruments and materials, in compliance with the treatment protocols, instructions and their conditions of use. Cases diagnosed as pulpitis and periodontitis were analyzed. Standard dental and endodontic instruments were used for treatment. The teeth were repaired with a photopolymer material. Anesthesia was determined by clinical case diagnosis (deterioration of chronic pulpitis of tooth 25). In access to the lumen, the roof of the pulp chamber was removed and the overhanging edges were excised. In parallel, the crown pulp was removed with a large diameter ball bar. Since both near-heart walls were destroyed by caries to the gingival level, it was necessary to repair in advance to ensure the quality in the root canal treatment. In the restoration plan after endodontic therapy, it was decided to repair the near-heart wall of tooth 25, including multiple teeth in the operation zone and meeting all the requirements for contact point formation. Cofadam was fitted after a complete reduction of the caries fossa. The contact surface of the 25th tooth was repaired with a photopolymer material in accordance with the rules of adhesion technique and aesthetic restoration. In the first stage of direct endodontic therapy, probing of the root canal mouth 3/1 was performed using a thin K-file under an antiseptic bath to determine the direction of the root canal course. If this step is neglected, a step may be formed, and a false course may be formed when the oral cavity is enlarged. The oral cavity was treated with a large tapered (12%) special rotating file with a funnel-shaped prepalat. The task was to remove the protruding dentin triangle and smooth the initial curvature of the lumen along the large curvature, creating conditions for good perfusion and sawdust removal. Next, determine the length of work, which is one of the most important stages of endodontic therapy. Since the stenosis of the root edge is usually located in the lumen at a distance of 0.5-1.0 mm from the radiological root edge, the tip of the instrument should be at this level, and the working length is considered a segment 0.5-1.0 mm shorter than the distance from

the radiologically defined root edge to the crown point. The working length was determined using the following recommended method. Using a table, find the length of the average tooth minus 0.5-1.0 mm. (If the crown is broken, the root length shall be the standard of measurement.) If you have an isometric diagnostic radiograph, an approximate number of working lengths can be obtained by measuring the indicators on the radiograph (Figure 6). In the CLCT-method, precise parameters are obtained by a special program (Figure 7). The lumen was perfused with a small amount of 5.25% sodium hypochlorite solution, and the excess liquid was removed with an aspirator. A diagnostic instrument (K-file #15) was inserted into the root canal to the stop. The stopper was attached to the selected crown point. I checked the level of the instrument in the root canal with the Apex locator. Next, X-ray aiming of the teeth was performed according to the rule of isometric projection with the instrument attached to the root canal. The tip of the instrument on the radiograph was located at a distance of 0.5-1.0 mm from the radiological apex of the tooth, so the working length was considered correctly determined. An endodontic ruler was used to mark the distance specified by the stopper in diagnostic K-file #15. When mechanically expanding the lumen, especially in a curved lumen, it is necessary to measure the working length again to avoid overstep of perforation and root edge stenosis. If the working length values measured by X-ray fluoroscopy and electrical measurement match, the apex locator can be used during the mechanical treatment of the lumen and the installation of the main gatta perch post. After determining the working length, the lumen contents were removed with a K-type instrument of maximum diameter, which could be used effortlessly.

Conclusion: Modern endodontics has a wide range of instruments and materials for mechanical, medical treatment and occlusion of root canals. At the same time, the root canal has individual characteristics (wide, narrow, straight, bent, calcified, incomplete formation, etc.), which makes it difficult to choose the optimal means and methods of endodontic therapy in connection with the stage of work and

with a particular clinical situation. From the results of scientific research and clinical observations, it was possible to propose recommendations on the choice of endodontic means and methods, taking into account the anatomical features of the tooth and the clinical manifestations of the inflammatory process. When determining the working length, it is recommended to refer to the table data and use the measured value of the Apex locator, but the X-ray isometric image with the instrument in the tube should be considered as the determining factor. On the radiograph, if the tip of the instrument is at a distance of 0.5-1.0 mm from the tip on the x-ray of the tooth, the working length is determined correctly and marked with a stopper.

All endodontic manipulations are carried out in the tube, strictly adhering to the working length. The instrument is used sequentially and step by step, without skipping the dimensions. Preparation requires maximum preservation of the natural luminal anatomy. The lumen is prepared in a moist environment so that the debris of the dentin can be removed by suction or adsorption by a turnder. In the preparation of the root canal tip, it is necessary to preserve dense dentin in the apical stenosis. Root canal treatment using modern technology requires the formation of appropriate skills and new scientific and clinical thinking of doctors.

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